

RE-DESIGNING RURAL EDUCATION THROUGH TRANSFORMATIVE PEDAGOGY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO RURAL SECTORS IN BENGALURU DISTRICT

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Abstract:

Education is in the Concurrent List and any issues relating to it is determined by both the Centre and the State Government concerned. The education is fundamental to development and growth. It promotes national interest and acts as an integrative force in society imparting values that foster national identity. The challenge of provision of quality education still remains. It goes without saying that quality education entails both teaching and learning. Many Studies have shown that technology can act as an effective agent of change in the classroom. It provides flexibility in teaching, learning, evaluating and gives immediate feedback, thus improving the quality of education in the country. It is essential to provide quality education for all including the excluded and the disadvantaged groups, especially in the rural sectors which will accelerate the growth and prosperity of the country. In fact, a successful education policy forms the bedrock of all fields of national development- political, economic, technical, scientific, social and environmental.

Key Words: Quality, Development, Growth, Technology, Feedback.

Introduction:

Every country needs a vision statement which stirs the imagination and motivates all segments of society to achieve greater heights. Sustained efforts are needed to tap the potentials of alternative methods of knowledge delivery for both school going and non-school going children including television, computerized self-learning and internet based courses. Successful population policy is directly linked to successful education policy. Success in raising literacy rates, school enrolment ratio, reducing dropout ratio in rural sector is a challenge.

Apart from addressing the needs of a large illiterate population in rural sectors, India's knowledge strategy must also develop innovative approaches to enhance knowledge acquisition among the large community of school dropouts. Extending the primary school system to over 5,00,000 villages in India has brought education to the masses. Unfortunately this huge quantitative expansion has been accompanied by a tremendous dilution in the quality of education. High dropout rates in rural areas is one result of single room schools with few teaching aids and inadequate instructions both in terms of quantity and quality. Hence it is a necessity to re-design the education in the rural areas. Quality improvement in the system can be accomplished by promoting centralized schools serving clusters of ten or more villages wherever distances and transportation links make that feasible. This will permit greater investment in educational infrastructure including introduction of computers.

Thus, an important role of education is to foster in each child the attributes and values of a responsible and healthy member of the family and society. The rigidity of curriculum, testing and teaching methods need to be transformed so that innovative methods and new models of education can be evolved, tested and implemented. Vocational courses have to be introduced and expanded to equip larger number of high school students in rural areas with occupation related knowledge and skills. Experiential learning is needed with new methods for knowledge delivery. Thus the progress of the whole nation will ultimately depend on the progress of its weakest link.

Title of the Paper:

Re-designing Rural Education through Transformative Pedagogy with special reference to Rural Sectors in Bengaluru District

Statement of Problem:

India's Education System has expanded but its current achievements are inadequate for the nation to realize its potential greatness. The problem faced in the rural sector is that net enrolment in schools are yet to improve, dropout rate increased. The traditional avenues of knowledge dissemination through education and printed information are ruled out. Thus there is a requirement for improvement in quality education which reflect a change in pedagogical methods.

Need and Background of the Study:

Education is the foundation for a vibrant democracy, growth of productivity and income and employment opportunities. Literacy is an indispensable minimum condition for development. The need of the study is to enhance quality education in rural sectors and to equip students with not only academic knowledge but also values and life knowledge. To make learning easy and interesting rural education in India is at a very grim state where students are not able to retain skills learnt in earlier classes. Thus education at rural level should have special facilities for preserving local art and culture and would provide also training in sports and skill development. The Background of the Study emphasises that education is fundamental to development and growth. It is the most important tool to reduce poverty, fostering knowledge and for building an equitable society.

Objectives:

- To enhance access and to improve quality education for all in rural sector.
- To promote equity through the inclusion of disadvantaged groups and weaker sections in rural sector.
- To provide vocational, experiential and value based education.
- To promote digital literacy in rural sector.

Scope of the Study:

The research is restricted to rural areas in the Bengaluru District.

Research Methodology:

The Archival Research Method is adopted. It is a method of collecting data from sources that already exists. The Secondary data is collected from journals, magazines, articles, reports, handbook and internet. This paper focuses on theoretical and conceptual analysis using textual descriptions to convey findings.

Review of Literature:

South Africa:

After Nelson Mandela became president in 1994, his government expanded access to schooling. It also replaced a school system segregated by race with one divided by wealth. Schools in poorer areas receive more state funding. But schools in richer areas can charge fees on top. More important than money are a lack of accountability and quality of the system.

Sweden:

Sven Stafstrom, Director General of the Swedish Research Council states that Sweden's research system has expanded over the past ten years, the result has been an increase in the quantity of research rather than improvement in quality.

Egypt:

The Egyptian President's Senior Education Advisor believes Egypt is in a good position for a world in which nations compete through innovations and ideas rather than commodities.

United Kingdom:

Roxanne Stockwell, Principal of Pearson College, London spoke to Times Higher Education, cites that college work is starting to offer some modules online. She states that if you are going to have innovations and challenge it has to be possible to enter qualitatively.

Source:

International News, Excerpted and adapted from The Economist and Times Higher Education, page No. 64, February 2017.

Data Analysis:

Table 1: The distribution of teacher training centers across four rural areas in Bengaluru District

Rural Areas	Number of Teacher Training Centers
Devanahalli	5
Doddaballapur	3
Kanakapura	4
Ramanagara	2

Source:

- Data extracted from various online directories and reports (2020-22)
 - Karnataka Department of Education
 - National University of Educational Planning & Administration
 - District Education Office, Bengaluru

Results:

- Devanahalli leads in teacher training infrastructure with five centres.
- Doddaballapur lag behind have fewer teacher training centres.
- Kanakapura emerges as a hub with four numbers.

Discussion:

- Devanahalli, with five centres cater to the training needs of surrounding rural areas.
- Doddaballapur may impact the quality and accessibility of education in this region.
- Kanakapura suggest a growing focus on educational development in this area.

- The implication is unequal distribution of resources, capacity building enhance teacher quality and may influence the attractiveness of teaching careers in these regions.

Table 2: Access to technology in the four rural areas of Bengaluru District

Rural Area	Internet Penetration %	Mobile Coverage %	Computer Literacy %	Digital Payment %
Devanahalli	65	90	55	70
Doddaballapur	45	80	40	50
Kanakapura	60	95	50	75
Ramanagara	50	85	45	60

Source:

- Data extracted from various online directories and reports (2020-22)
 - Indian Telecom Regulatory Authority of India.
 - National Sample Survey Office.
 - Reserve Bank of India
 - District Administration, Bengaluru

Results:

- Internet penetration is highest in Devanahalli. It shows the percentage of households with internet access.
- Mobile Coverage is highest in Kanakapura.
- Computer Literacy shows the percentage of population with basic computer skills. It is highest in Devanahalli.
- The percentage of transactions made through digital modes is highest in Kanakapura.

Discussion:

- There is a significant disparities in internet penetration and computer literacy across rural areas.
- Mobile coverage is relatively better, but there should be scope for improvement.
- Digital payment adoption is at varying levels with Devanahalli and Kanakapura is leading.
- There is opportunity for growth if invested in digital infrastructure & literacy programs.

Findings:

- From the current pedagogical practices in rural places, it is found that system followed is Teacher-Centered and it involves rote learning.
- It is found that lot of challenges are faced by teachers like limited resources, lack of training and high student-teacher ratio.
- It is found that in rural places students are less motivated.
- It is found that in rural areas there is limited access to technology and poor infrastructure.
- It is found that transformative pedagogy system is not in practice.

Recommendations & Suggestions:

- It is suggested that education system should be contextualized. It is essential to incorporate local knowledge and culture into the system.
- It is recommended to foster inclusive education by giving importance to diversity, equity and social justice.
- It is recommended to integrate technology by enhancing access, engagement and learning outcomes.
- It is suggested that teachers training should be provided with focus on transformative pedagogy and technology integration.
- It is suggested that community involvement should be encouraged. It is essential to engage local stakeholders in institution development.

Conclusion:

The Education is fundamental to development and growth. Education should reach to the nook and corner of all rural sectors. The pattern of knowledge disseminated to the rural sector should transform the entire area. Re-designing qualitative improvements in education at rural sector should reflect a change in pedagogical methods from passive learning to active learning, develop critical thinking and be practical oriented. Thus transformative pedagogy has the potential to re-design rural education in Bengaluru district.

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